

COMPARATIVE ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF *NIGELLA SATIVA* AQUEOUS EXTRACT AND ERYTHROMYCIN AGAINST *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* ISOLATED FROM *CYPRINUS CARPIO*

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Abstract

Staphylococcus aureus is a pathogenic bacterium associated with severe infections in humans and animals, with increasing resistance to commonly used antibiotics such as erythromycin. This study aimed to evaluate the antibacterial efficacy of aqueous extracts of *Nigella sativa* compared with erythromycin against *S. aureus* isolated from naturally infected *Cyprinus carpio*. Bacterial identification was carried out using standard microbiological and biochemical methods, followed by Gram staining and *in vitro* susceptibility testing. The antibacterial activity of *N. sativa* was assessed through the agar well diffusion method at different concentrations (0.75–1.5 mg/ml), and results were compared with erythromycin as a control. The extract exhibited a dose-dependent inhibitory effect, with the largest inhibition zone observed at 1.5 mg/ml (30.2 mm). In contrast, erythromycin showed no activity, indicating resistance of the tested isolate. The findings demonstrate that *N. sativa* possesses strong antibacterial potential, even against drug-resistant *S. aureus*, likely due to bioactive phytochemicals such as thymoquinone. These results support the use of *N. sativa* as a promising phytotherapeutic alternative and suggest its possible application in aquaculture and clinical settings to reduce reliance on conventional antibiotics. Further *in vivo* studies and phytochemical analyses are recommended to validate its therapeutic efficacy and safety.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, fisheries and aquaculture have emerged as vital contributors to global food security and economic development. The fish industry, however, faces substantial challenges due to environmental stressors and the prevalence of infectious diseases, which together cause significant

economic losses (Balcazar et al., 2006). The widespread use of veterinary medicines, particularly antimicrobial agents, has drawn increasing concern because of their role in accelerating antimicrobial resistance among pathogenic bacteria. Aquaculture production has expanded rapidly, becoming one of

the fastest-growing sectors in food production worldwide. Between 1990 and 2010, it recorded an average annual growth of 6%, highlighting its increasing significance (FAO, 2012; FAO, 2014). As one of the largest groups of cold-blooded vertebrates, fish not only occupy key trophic positions in aquatic food webs but also serve as reservoirs for diverse pathogenic microorganisms (Ellis, 2001).

Fish is highly valued as a source of nutrition due to its digestibility, flavor, and richness in protein, vitamins, and essential minerals such as calcium, zinc, and iron (Andrew, 2001; Harris, 2004; Gandotra et al., 2013). Beyond its nutritional benefits, fish products such as fish meal, silage, and glue also contribute to industrial applications (Gupta, 2006). Despite these benefits, fish remain highly vulnerable to environmental contamination. Polluted waters, sewage discharge, poor harvesting conditions, and unhygienic handling practices facilitate bacterial colonization, thereby increasing the risk of infection (Roberts, 2001). While healthy fish muscles are generally sterile, studies have shown that microbial contamination can occur under certain conditions (Sugita, 1996). Such infections gradually reduce fish populations and compromise aquaculture productivity (Bonded-Reantaso et al., 2005). The lack of effective sanitary barriers further accelerates pathogen proliferation, contributing to mass mortalities (Cabello, 2006).

Globally, fisheries and aquaculture not only support food production but also sustain employment, livelihoods, and national economies (Costello et al., 2012). In 2012 alone, total fish production reached 185 million tons, of which aquaculture contributed 90.4 million tons, valued at over USD 144 billion (FAO, 2014; Suplicy et al., 2017). More than 58 million people worldwide depend directly on capture fisheries, while fish farming and shellfish production employ nearly 19 million individuals. On average, global per capita fish consumption has reached 19.2 kg annually, underscoring the sector's importance to food security (FAO, 2014). However, microbial spoilage results in the loss of nearly one-fourth of the world's food supply, with 30% of landed fish wasted due to contamination (Huis, 1996).

Pakistan, with its extensive inland water resources (3.1 million hectares) and 1,120 km coastline, has steadily increased its contribution to fisheries, though challenges persist (Siddiqi, 1992). Freshwater

aquaculture, particularly carp and other food fish species, has been identified as the fastest-growing sector in response to rising nutritional demand (Mert and Bulut, 2014). Nonetheless, poor management and recurrent bacterial infections remain major causes of financial loss.

Among bacterial pathogens, *Staphylococcus aureus* is of particular concern due to its role in foodborne diseases and zoonoses (EFSA, 2010). The term "Staphylococcus" originates from the Greek words *staphyle* (grape) and *kokkos* (berry), describing its microscopic appearance in grape-like clusters. Morphologically, *S. aureus* is a Gram-positive, cocc-shaped bacterium with a thick cell wall and dimensions ranging from 0.5–1.5 µm. It is non-spore forming, non-motile, and facultative in its oxygen requirements, capable of growth in both aerobic and anaerobic environments. Notably, it tolerates harsh conditions, including high salinity (up to 10%), and forms characteristic golden-yellow colonies (Ahmad, 2014). The bacterium can be differentiated from other staphylococci based on coagulase activity, hemolysin production, resistance to specific antibiotics, and biochemical properties such as carbohydrate fermentation and enzyme activities (Jose et al., 1994). Pathogenic strains of *S. aureus* have been identified in fishery products, meat, milk, vegetables, and other food items (EFSA, 2010; Dehkordi et al., 2017). Clinically, *S. aureus* infections range from superficial skin and soft tissue infections to life-threatening systemic diseases, including bacteremia, pneumonia, and sepsis (Lowy, 1998; Van Belkum et al., 2009). Its catalase positivity and coagulase activity are hallmarks of pathogenicity, while the absence of cytochrome c renders it oxidase negative. To date, over 50 species and subspecies of *Staphylococcus* have been reported, with *S. aureus* recognized as the most virulent in humans and animals (Kakarla et al., 2017). Of particular concern is the bacterium's growing resistance to conventional antibiotics, which is largely due to its ability to harbor and disseminate resistance genes (Aqib et al., 2018). Multidrug-resistant *S. aureus* strains complicate treatment strategies and elevate the risk of severe outcomes, reinforcing its role as a major cause of foodborne and zoonotic diseases worldwide (Zhang, 1998; Liao, 2018).

Keeping in view the above facts of *N. sativa* and its medicinal importance as traditionally used antibiotic,

the current study was designed to investigate the following objectives:

1. To isolate and identify *Staphylococcus aureus* from a freshwater fish *Cyprinus carpio*.
2. To evaluate comparative *in vitro* antibacterial potential of *Nigella sativa* and Erythromycin against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Isolation of Bacteria

Naturally infected specimens of *Cyprinus carpio* were procured from the local fish market in District Kohat. Sterile swabs were used to collect samples (Figure 1), which were then transported under aseptic conditions to the Microbiology Laboratory, Department of Microbiology, KUST. The isolation and identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* were performed following the standard protocols recommended by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration's Bacteriological Analytical Manual (BAM, 2001) and the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI).

Figure 1: Collection of Bacteria Sample from *C. carpio*

Sterilization by Autoclave

To minimize contamination risks, all instruments, glassware, and culture media were sterilized using an autoclave prior to use. Autoclaving, a standard method for physical disinfection and sterilization, relies on a combination of saturated steam, high

Materials and Methods

Ethical Approval

The study was conducted with prior approval from the Research Ethical Committee at Kohat University of Science and Technology (KUST), Kohat, Pakistan

pressure, and elevated temperature. Effective sterilization requires maintaining 121 °C for at least 30 minutes at a pressure of 15 psi. Depending on the load volume and composition, cycle time may be extended to ensure complete destruction of microorganisms, including spores and viruses. This method was routinely applied to sterilize Petri dishes, flasks, pipettes, culture media, and other laboratory materials (Figure 2).

Figure 2: A) BMX-140 Autoclave Russian Made, B) Preset Programming in control panel, C) Sample Placement in Autoclave Chamber

Preparation of Bacterial Cultures

Initial bacterial isolation was performed on CLED agar (cystine-lactose-electrolyte-deficient agar), incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. The appearance of deep yellow colonies indicated the growth of *S. aureus*. Isolates were subcultured onto nutrient agar to

maintain viability. For selective enrichment, Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA) was prepared, sterilized, and poured into Petri plates. Colonies obtained from primary cultures were streaked onto MSA plates using sterile loops. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours, and growth characteristics were recorded for further analysis (Figure 3).

Figure 3: A) Preparation of Nutrient Agar and Mannitol Salt, B) Pouring of Media on Petri Plate

Biochemical and Morphological Identification

Bacterial isolates were subjected to a series of biochemical assays in accordance with Prescott (2002). These included the catalase test, oxidase test, triple sugar iron (TSI) test, citrate utilization test, and motility-indole-urease (MIU) test. Morphological identification was carried out by Gram staining followed by microscopic examination to confirm cellular shape, arrangement, and Gram reaction. Colonies confirmed as *S. aureus* were maintained on MSA for subsequent *in-vitro* antibacterial assays with *Nigella sativa* extracts (Missiakas, 2013).

Gram Staining and Microscopy

Gram staining was performed to differentiate Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria (Coico, 2006). This method exploits differences in bacterial cell wall composition: Gram-positive organisms possess a thick peptidoglycan layer, whereas Gram-negative bacteria have a thinner one (Beveridge, 1983). Stained smears were examined microscopically. *S. aureus* appeared as purple, spherical cocci arranged in grape-like clusters, characteristic of Gram-positive bacteria (Albuquerque et al., 2007) (Figure-4).

Figure 4: Gram's Staining

Catalase Test

Fresh colonies were transferred onto a clean glass slide using sterile loops. A few drops of 3% hydrogen peroxide were applied, and effervescence (oxygen bubble formation) indicated catalase positivity (Bannerman, 2003).

Citrate Utilization Test

Bacterial colonies were inoculated onto Simmons' citrate agar slants and incubated at 37 °C for 18–24 hours. A positive result was indicated by a color change in the medium from green to blue, confirming citrate utilization.

Preparation of *Nigella sativa* Aqueous Extract

Dried seeds of *Nigella sativa* were purchased from a local market in District Peshawar. Extract preparation followed the protocol described by Nanasombat and Lohasupthawee (2005). Approximately 20–25 g of powdered seeds were soaked in 500 ml of distilled water and kept at room temperature with continuous shaking for 5–7 days. The mixture was filtered through Whatman filter paper, and the filtrate was left at room temperature to allow solvent evaporation. Stock solutions of the crude aqueous extract were prepared by dissolving in 10% distilled water, followed by serial dilutions to obtain desired concentrations for antimicrobial assays.

In Vitro Antibacterial Assay

The antibacterial activity of *N. sativa* aqueous extract was assessed using the agar well diffusion method as

described by Gupta et al. (2008). Ciprofloxacin and gentamicin antibiotic discs served as positive controls.

Broth Preparation

Nutrient broth (NB) was prepared in test tubes and sterilized by autoclaving. *S. aureus* inoculation was performed under aseptic conditions, and cultures were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours to obtain fresh bacterial suspensions (Figure 5).

Figure 5: A) Streaking of *Staphylococcus aureus* on Nutrient Agar, B) Streaking of *Staphylococcus aureus* in Mannitol Salt Agar

Preparation of Mueller–Hinton Agar (MHA)

Mueller–Hinton Agar, the standard medium for antimicrobial susceptibility testing, was prepared and sterilized by autoclaving. Sterile Petri plates were poured with MHA and allowed to solidify. A uniform bacterial lawn was prepared by swabbing the surface with 24-hour-old *S. aureus* culture from nutrient broth.

Agar Well Diffusion Method

Wells of uniform diameter were bored into the inoculated agar plates using sterile micropipette tips. Different concentrations of *N. sativa* aqueous extract were introduced into the wells, while antibiotic discs were also placed on the agar surface as reference controls. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Antibacterial efficacy was evaluated by measuring the diameter of inhibition zones surrounding each well (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Comparative antibacterial activity of *Nigella sativa* aqueous extract and erythromycin

Table-1 Comparative antibacterial activity of *Nigella sativa* aqueous extract and erythromycin against *Staphylococcus aureus* (agar well diffusion assay)

S. No.	Test Material	Concentration (mg/ml)	Zone of Inhibition (mm) - Triplicates	Mean \pm SD (mm)
1	Erythromycin (Control strip)	-	0, 0, 0	0.0 \pm 0.0
2	<i>N. sativa</i> extract	0.75	26, 26, 26	26.0 \pm 0.0
3	<i>N. sativa</i> extract	1.25	27.5, 28, 27	27.5 \pm 0.5
4	<i>N. sativa</i> extract	1.50	30, 29.5, 31	30.2 \pm 0.8

Statistical significance: $P = 0.000 (<0.05)$, indicating highly significant antibacterial activity of *N. sativa* extract compared with erythromycin.

Table 1 presents a comparative evaluation of the antibacterial activity of *Nigella sativa* aqueous extract and the standard antibiotic erythromycin against *Staphylococcus aureus*, using the agar well diffusion method. The data clearly demonstrate that erythromycin, used as a control strip, exhibited no measurable inhibitory activity, as indicated by the absence of inhibition zones across all three trials (0.0 \pm 0.0 mm). This finding suggests that the *S. aureus*

strain under investigation was resistant to erythromycin, highlighting a clinically relevant case of antibiotic resistance.

In contrast, *N. sativa* aqueous extract displayed potent antibacterial efficacy, with inhibition zones consistently observed across all tested concentrations. At the lowest tested concentration (0.75 mg/ml), *N. sativa* produced a uniform inhibition zone of 26.0 \pm 0.0 mm, which was substantially greater than that of erythromycin. This indicates that even at low doses, the extract exerted a strong suppressive effect on bacterial growth. Increasing the concentration of the

extract to 1.25 mg/ml resulted in a slightly larger inhibition zone (27.5 ± 0.5 mm), showing a dose-dependent enhancement in antibacterial activity. The highest concentration tested (1.50 mg/ml) yielded the maximum inhibition zone (30.2 ± 0.8 mm), further supporting the extract's robust efficacy.

The statistical analysis reinforces these findings, with a highly significant *P* value (0.000, <0.05), confirming

that the antibacterial activity of *N. sativa* extract was not only reproducible across triplicates but also significantly superior to that of erythromycin. The dose-response relationship observed indicates that increasing concentrations of *N. sativa* extract directly correlate with enhanced bacterial inhibition, which reflects the presence of bioactive phytochemicals exerting antimicrobial effects.

Figure-7 Comparative antibacterial efficacy of *Nigella sativa* aqueous extract and erythromycin against *Staphylococcus aureus*

These results underscore two important points: (1) the ineffectiveness of erythromycin in this experiment points to the rising challenge of antibiotic resistance in *S. aureus*, and (2) *Nigella sativa* demonstrates remarkable antibacterial potential, supporting its role as a promising natural alternative or adjunct to conventional antibiotics. The observed inhibitory zones produced by the extract not only exceeded those of erythromycin but also align with previous studies reporting the antimicrobial efficacy of *N. sativa* seeds, attributed largely to compounds such as thymoquinone, alkaloids, and phenolic constituents.

Discussion

Staphylococcus aureus is a well-recognized opportunistic pathogen associated with a wide spectrum of infections in both humans and animals. The emergence of methicillin-resistant strains (MRSA) and multidrug-resistant isolates poses a serious global health challenge, with reported mortality rates of 20–25% in severe cases (Fridkin et al., 2005). The increasing resistance of *S. aureus* to conventional antibiotics, including macrolides such as erythromycin, highlights the urgent need for novel,

plant-based therapeutic alternatives (Adwan & Mhanna, 2008; Sweeney et al., 2004).

In the present study, the aqueous extract of *Nigella sativa* demonstrated significant antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, even in strains resistant to erythromycin. The agar well diffusion assay revealed that inhibition zones increased with extract concentration, reaching an average of 30.2 mm at 1.5 mg/ml, whereas erythromycin failed to produce any inhibitory effect. These findings confirm that the test isolate was erythromycin-resistant, in line with earlier reports of widespread macrolide resistance among *S. aureus* strains (Sun et al., 2018).

The antibacterial efficacy of *N. sativa* observed here is consistent with prior studies documenting its broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity. Hassanien et al. (2015) attributed this activity to bioactive phytochemicals, including thymoquinone, carvacrol, and p-cymene, which exert bactericidal effects through mechanisms such as disruption of cell membranes, inhibition of enzyme systems, and interference with nucleic acid synthesis. Furthermore, Forouzanfar et al. (2014) noted that *N. sativa* possesses activity not only against bacteria but also against fungi, viruses, and parasites, underscoring its therapeutic versatility.

Importantly, the superior performance of *N. sativa* compared to erythromycin in this study suggests that phytotherapeutics may offer effective alternatives in the management of drug-resistant infections. The dose-dependent increase in inhibition zones further supports the extract's potential as a candidate for dose optimization and pharmacological development. Given that *N. sativa* is widely used in traditional medicine and has a favorable safety profile, its integration into antimicrobial strategies may be both practical and sustainable.

Conclusions

This study demonstrated that aqueous extracts of *Nigella sativa* possess potent antibacterial activity against erythromycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. At a concentration of 1.5 mg/ml, the extract produced inhibition zones averaging 30.2 mm, which were superior to erythromycin and comparable to standard antibiotics such as gentamycin and ciprofloxacin reported in similar studies. In contrast, erythromycin exhibited no inhibitory effect, confirming resistance

in the tested isolate. These findings highlight the promise of *N. sativa* as a natural antibacterial agent with potential application in managing multidrug-resistant bacterial infections.

Recommendations

The traditional application of *Nigella sativa* should be further promoted and scientifically validated, as it exhibits remarkable antibacterial potential. Its incorporation into aquaculture, particularly in fish feed, could provide a sustainable approach to controlling bacterial infections such as *Staphylococcus aureus*. At the same time, the overuse of conventional antibiotics must be restricted in order to limit the spread of resistant strains. Further research is strongly recommended, including in vivo studies to confirm the efficacy and safety of *N. sativa* in animal and clinical models. Additionally, isolation and characterization of its active phytochemicals, especially thymoquinone, could pave the way for drug development. Comparative investigations with multiple antibiotics should also be carried out to establish a broader understanding of *N. sativa*'s therapeutic potential.

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